

Terpene synthase gene amplicons from subseafloor sediment

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We sequenced putative terpene synthase (TS) gene fragments. These fragments were amplified using subseafloor sediment sample collected off Shimokita Peninsula, Japan, and primers targeting bacterial geosmin and 2-methylisoborneol synthases. Amplicons were sequenced using Illumina platform. This technical note describes details of raw read processing and OTU taxonomic annotation.

Processing of raw reads obtained in next-generation sequencing of PCR amplicons

The obtained sequences were processed in the AmpliconTagger v1.3.0 pipeline (1). In brief, raw reads were scanned for sequencing adapters and PhiX spike-in sequences. Remaining paired-end reads were filtered for quality so that sequences that had 1 N or more; had average quality scores lower than 25; or had more than 60 nucleotides with a Phred quality score lower than 15 were removed. The remaining paired-end reads were assembled into their full amplicon sequences using their overlapping common parts using FLASH v1.2.11 (2). Assembled sequences were de-replicated at 100% identity and clustered at 99% identity using VSEARCH v2.7.1 (3). Clusters having less than 10 reads were discarded. Remaining clusters were clustered again at 97% identity to generate Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs). These OTUs were filtered for chimeras using VSEARCH's implementation of UCHIME *de novo*. Custom geosmin and 2-MIB reference databases were used. Briefly, for each data type (geosmin and 2-MIB), final OTUs were blasted against the NCBI nt database. Hits with an e-value < 1e-20, alignment length ≥ 100 and alignment percentage ≥ 60 were kept to build the RDP training set. RDP training sets were generated as previously described (<https://github.com/jtremlay/RDP-training-sets>). The RDP classifier (4) was then used with this training set to assign a taxonomic lineage to each OTU. The RDP classifier gave

a score (0 to 1) to each taxonomic depth of each OTUs. Each taxonomic depth having a score ≥ 0.5 was kept to reconstruct the final lineage. Taxonomic lineages assigned to bacterial or archaeal lineages were combined with the OTUs abundance matrix obtained above to generate a raw OTU table. The sequence-specific primer sequences were removed using MEGA v.7.0.26 (5).

The obtained OTUs were annotated using blastX algorithm (6) and NCBI GenBank non-redundant protein sequence database (nr, accessed October – November 2020). Non-TS OTUs were excluded.

References

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